

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

Deliverable 5.4 – 1st Report on Dissemination & Communication

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Project overview	6
2. Methodology & Scope of the report	6
2.1. Scope and organization of the document	7
2.2. DCE targets & Achievements.....	7
2.3. Target Groups	10
3. Communication tools	12
3.1. Project website	12
3.2. Social media.....	13
3.3. E-newsletters	19
3.4. Press releases/Apearances in the media	19
3.5. Other materials	20
3.6. Internal communication	21
3.6.1. Trello platform	21
3.6.2. PMB monthly meetings.....	21
4. Dissemination and exploitation activities	22
4.1. International Scientific Conference	23
4.2. Local meetings for mapping and engagement.....	24
4.3. Open-access scientific publications in high-rated journals	25
4.4. Policy briefs.....	27
4.5. Participation in external events, scientific congresses and conferences	27
4.6. Dissemination and exploitation through partners' networking resources.....	28
5. Monitoring and Evaluation	29
6. Conclusion and recommendations	30
7. Annexes	32

Table of Tables

Table 1. DCE instruments, target groups and measurable targets	7
Table 2. Dissemination and communication activities participation summary	11
Table 3. Social media accounts of GreenFORCE	14
Table 4. Social Media GreenForce – cut of date 30/06/2023	15
Table 5. Social Media Reach on partners’ social media channels– cut of date 30/06/2023	17
Table 6. Newsletter reach	19
Table 7. PMB meetings	22
Table 8. Documentation of dissemination events	23
Table 9. Local meetings for mapping and engagement in the WB countries	24
Table 10. List of deliverables and products uploaded in Zenodo	25
Table 11. List of deliverables and products uploaded in GERY	26
Table 12. KPI achievements of dissemination and communication	29
Table 13. Web Page Top 50 Posts Overview – for period	32
Table 14. Table for detailed reporting on dissemination events and activities - year 1	34
Table 15. Table for detailed reporting on dissemination events and activities year 1 - continued	35
Table 16. Social Media Reach on partners’ social media channels – cut of date 30/06/2023	36

Table of Figures

Figure 1. The target groups of GreenFORCE	10
Figure 2. Dissemination event participants’ distribution	12
Figure 3. Project Website	13
Figure 4. Posts Overview	13
Figure 5. GreenFORCE Twitter account	14
Figure 6. GreenFORCE Facebook page	14
Figure 7. GreenFORCE Instagram account	14
Figure 8. LinkedIn account	14
Figure 9. Youtube account	14
Figure 10. GreenFORCE Social media reach distribution	17
Figure 11. Social media snapshots	18
Figure 12. GreenFORCE Newsletter 1	19
Figure 13. GreenFORCE Newsletter 2	19
Figure 14. Example of project’s branding tools used	20
Figure 15. GreenFORCE board on Trello platform - snapshot	21
Figure 16. GreenFORCE PMB meetings and Trello source	22
Figure 17. Excerpt from presentations from GreenFORCE partners in the International Scientific Conference on Green Agenda for Western Balkans, Belgrade	23
Figure 18. Excerpt from the works of the stakeholders on co-design workshop	24
Figure 19. Zenodo repository GreenFORCE	25
Figure 20. GERY repository (GEography RepositoRY University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography) GreenFORCE	26

List of abbreviations used in this document

DCE: Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation

EREA: European Research Executive Agency

GA: Grant agreement

KPIs: Key Performance Indicators

NGOs: Non-governmental organisations

PMB: Project Management Board

PC: Project Coordinator

R&I: Research and Innovation

WB: Western Balkan

WBC: Western Balkan Countries

WP: Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable D5.4 – 1st Report on Communication and Dissemination is the report directly related to the outputs and outcomes stemming from the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities of the project. This is a document for the use of all the partners involved in GreenFORCE project, designated as well as “public” regarding the dissemination level.

The deliverable is with a cut-off date 30/06/2023 covering the first year of implementation of the project. It intends to summarise in a concise manner communication and dissemination efforts during this period of GreenFORCES’ implementation. Furthermore, the deliverable will provide insights for evaluation of the achievements of the dissemination and communication and the possible changes necessary for the alteration and update of the project’s DCE Strategy.

1. Project overview

GreenFORCE aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" scientific research and innovation of Co-PLAN (Albania), CEA (North Macedonia), and UB-GEF (Serbia), as a means to enhancing their research profile, strengthening research and management capacities of their staff, and contributing to convergence between Western Balkans (WB) and EU research capacities, as well as to wider policy initiatives for the WB region.

This objective is reached through the twinning partnership of five organisations that will work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning; will transfer and exchange knowledge among partner organisations through applying the knowledge management cycle; and will engage in networking for sharing, cross-fertilizing and amplifying knowledge at the societal level. Ultimately, the ambition is to transcend from individual learning to enabling institutional learning, making sure that research and research management practices become institutionalised within the recipient organisations. GreenFORCE will contribute to the impacts of the destination "Improved access to excellence" by enabling pathways of cooperation, exchange, co-design, co-creation with academia, civil society and policy-makers at the regional level.

The 5 partner organisations are: Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development in Albania as the coordinating partner; University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (UB-GEF) in Serbia and Center for Economic Analyses Association (CEA) in North Macedonia, as the two regional partners; and Nordregio, a pan-Nordic research organization based in Sweden, together with Politecnico di Torino, Italy (POLITO), as the leading EU research institutions. POLIS University in Albania is the affiliate partner of Co-PLAN.

2. Methodology & Scope of the report

The 1st Report on communication, dissemination and exploitation (DCE) reflects on the tasks and activities implemented in the first year (1/7/2022-30/06/2023) of the GreenFORCE project within all Work Packages (WPs) and tasks incorporated in each of the WPs. The partners have jointly worked on creating the [Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation \(DCE\) Strategy](#), which is a publicly available document (Deliverable 5.1) and the partners have agreed on the implementation of the DCE Strategy in October 2022. The DCE Strategy will be revised

in month 18 of the project's life time thus based on the information gathered the recommendations of this report will add value.

This report is focusing on the assessment of the activities conducted regarding the planned activities of the project during the past period, presenting them via the different tools and activities used their efficiency and effectiveness as well in communicating and disseminating the projects' messages.

The data and information summarized and reported are based on the collected reporting tools and templates that are needed for reporting by the contracting authority as well as the project's reporting and recording templates developed as part of the DCE strategy.

2.1. Scope and organization of the document

This Deliverable D5.4 presents a review of the activities carried out by the GreenFORCE consortium to communicate and disseminate the activities it developed in the first twelve months of the project and to raise awareness of the project itself and of the support. The document also provides information about the different initiatives aimed at exploitation of the project results.

Based on this overall scope, the document is organized in two main sections. The first section followed by the project summary overview, reflects the agreed outputs that the reports is referring to with the goals for effectively differentiating communication, dissemination and exploitation, as well as quantifies and explains the achievements and level of completion of the targets for the reporting period. Then, the dissemination and exploitation activities carried out per communication tool used are elaborated and presented in detail. In each of these sections a brief description of their objective and target audience/stakeholder and of the procedure to get access to the associated information is provided as well.

2.2. DCE targets & Achievements

The project has defined the targets and instruments for DCE, and the table below presents the achievement levels for the reporting period for the defined target.

Table 1. DCE instruments, target groups and measurable targets

DCE medium and means	General target groups	Measurable targets (and WP involved)	Level of completeness / Achievements
Project branding (logo and templates)	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	Project logo design, and overall brand identity i.e.: colour palette, formatting (leaflet, brochure, rollup banner, press releases, policy articles, e-newsletter, etc.); project roll-up banner (5 in total/1 per country); 1000 brochures with infographics; 400 leaflets reaching at least 1000 recipients. (WP5)	Project branding identity markings – branding identity completed and used throughout the activities and tasks. E-Newsletter template developed – Newsletter No.1 prepared and disseminated, No2 prepared and disseminated Rollup banner designed and printed (each partner has its own banner) 70 project factsheets prepared and disseminated

Project website, referred as a primary source by social media	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	1000 page views per year, 3000 in total. (WP5)	Website created and functional Y1 web page views 3.192 (total users: 902) Social media overall reach: 96,847; (Partners' social media channels 40,153; GreenFORCE social media channels reach: 56,694)
Social networks (Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and, Researchgate)	Policy makers; Stakeholders; Academic sector	Over 400 followers; at least 1 FB post per week; 1 twitter message per week; 1 message per week in LinkedIn, 1 IG post per week, 3 YT videos in total. (WP5)	Followers (30/06/2023): -Tweeter 21 followers - FB 128 followers -Instagram 154 followers -Linked in: 160 followers Weekly posts uploaded – total of 34 on each social media project channel (30/06/2023) Website posts: >50
E-newsletter (connected to weblog) informing experts on project deliverables/results useful for other practitioners	Policy makers; Stakeholders	1000 subscribers ¹ ; Published 2 times per year; 6 times in 3 years. (WP5)	Newsletter 1: 71 subscribers (sent invitation for subscription to over 600 via email) Newsletter 2: 255 subscribers (post on social media for visibility and additional subscriptions)
Media-releases: articles in newspapers, magazines, impact on radio or TV	General public	Drafting press releases for national TVs and other web-portals, at least twice a year by each WB partner. (WP5)	Press release prepared for 1 st Conference in Belgrade
Scientific conferences	Academic sector and practitioners	2 international scientific conferences in the WB organised by the WB partner universities, at least 200 recipients; One final event at least 50 recipients; One workshop on "green transition in the WB" at the EWRC; contribution to or co-organisation of regional events with RCC, NALAS and TG-WeB. (WP2, WP4, WP5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1st Conference in Belgrade, in June 2023, organized by partner UBGEF, 189 participants ○ RSA Special Session for WB, in June 2023: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -3 papers from the partners, participants and researchers of GreenFORCE; -special session participants: 11; ○ -promoted project at RSA international ambassador meeting (~60 participants) Contribution to the 2023 annual Tg-WeB workshop: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Participants: 12 physical + ~20 online ○ Organization of Roundtable on 'Just green transition' at the AESOP Conference, 25-29 July 2022 in Tartu, Estonia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Panellists in roundtable: 5 persons - Participants: 15 persons ○ Participation and presenting the concept of 'just green transition' at the National Forum on Climate Change, organized within the Green-AL project, led by Co-PLAN.

¹ The subscriber number will be revised if necessary in the DCE strategy revision in month 18th

			Presentation in the Annual Congress of AESOP, in Lodz Poland, from POLITO on Just Green Transition practices
Annual meeting	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	At least one annual meeting of TG-WeB. (WP4, WP5)	TG-Web annual meeting 2023, in Skopje, May 2023, ~30 participants online & physical presence, including partners
Policy briefs/reports	Project partners; Policy makers	5 policy briefs published in journals (WP2, WP5)	2 policy briefs in preparation: (expected to be sent out to decision making stakeholders by December 2023) (Fiona Imami is drafting a policy brief on transition fatigue; Merita Toska and Rodion Gjoka are drafting a policy brief on 'Waste to Energy: The Potential of Alternative Fuels in the Western Balkans').
Open lectures	Project partners; Academic sector	1 per University/per teaching event 3 in total. (WP3, WP5)	Teaching events at POLIS University of: -POLITO:2 weeks in May 2023 with 35 students. -UB-GEF and CEA: In March 2023 with 26 participants.
Large dissemination Events	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	3 large dissemination events (up to 250 participants). (WP5)	Belgrade Conferences June 2023, 189 participants
Final dissemination event	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	At least 50 participants. (WP5)	/
Open-access publications in Scientific journals	Academic sector; Policy makers; Stakeholders	Drafting and submitting for publication 3 joint scientific papers based on the research of WP4, and at least 1 paper per WB organisation, focusing on own country (WP3,WP5)	Open access to the outputs: uploaded on Zenodo (https://rb.gy/iq8em) & GERY (https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/1385)

Open-access book	Project partners; Programme authorities; Policy makers; Business community; Academic sector and citizenships	Drafting the content for 1 edited open-access book (WP3)	Content drafted, proposal prepared & sent, to Palgrave MacMillan, proposed 4 parts, 27 chapters. (https://trello.com/c/LcohX2ME/53-deliverable-32-application-package-submitted-for-the-edited-book)
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2.3. Target Groups

Dissemination tools do take into consideration the stakeholder groups difference when necessary/appropriate.

Figure 1. The target groups of GreenFORCE

The main groups of stakeholders or target audiences for the GreenFORCE’s communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are:

- Core group of 29 researchers from the consortium – (17 from the WB partners & 12 from the EU partners);
- Researchers connected to, but not directly linked to GreenFORCE however interacting with the project.
- Societal actors directly benefiting from dissemination, exploitation and networking: a) students and scientists - from the WB; b) policy makers and other societal actors related to green transition CSOs and industries,
- Society at large.

The table below presents the participation of different stakeholders in each event with a total reach of 642 participants in the first year of project implementation. The distribution of reached target group is presented in the figure following, indicating the coverage by target group. The distribution indicates that the most informed audience so far are the researchers within and outside the consortium with over two-thirds of the audience.

In the coming period as the project activities will deliver other outputs it is expected that the other target groups will be further included and the participation of the societal actors to increase. The society at large is also a relevant target group which is reached more robustly via the other communication tools, such as via meetings, social media and the webpage, which is reported in the other sections. (See annex tables for more details).

Table 2. Dissemination and communication activities participation summary

Dissemination and communication activities linked to the project			Actual number of participants reach (after 1 month)
ID (PXX_XX_dd.mm.yyyy)	Type of activity	Title	
Co-PLAN_WP1_1.1_04.07.2022	Meeting	Kick-off meeting of GreenFORCE Project	29
CO-PLAN_WP4.1_08.11.2022	Workshop	Co-Design Workshop on the Conceptualization of the Green Transition in the Western Balkan – part 1	44
CO-PLAN_WP4.1_22.11.2022	Workshop	Co-Design Workshop on the Conceptualization of the Green Transition in the Western Balkan – part 2	33
POLITO_WP_3.1/1_01.12.2022	Collaboration meeting	Scientific Publication Plan Co-Design Workshop	22
NORD_COPLAN__WP_2.1/1_02.12.2022	Collaboration meeting	Shared Strategic Research Agenda - Workshop	20
POLITO_WP_3.1_23.01.2023	Collaboration meeting	Scientific Publication Plan Co-Design Workshop	19
NORD__WP_2.4/1_24.01.2023	Collaboration meeting	SEMINAR & WORKSHOP: Writing policy briefs	18
NORD_COPLAN__WP_2.1/2_24.01.2023	Collaboration meeting	Shared Strategic Research Agenda - Workshop	18
POLITO_Co-PLAN_WP1_1.2_01.04.2023	Collaborative meeting	Research Advisory Board meeting	19
Nordregio_Co-PLAN_WP2_03.2023	Forum	National Forum 'Climate change in Albania'	95
Nordregio_Co-PLAN_WP2_03.2023	Workshop	Alberto workshop in POLIS	11
POLIS_UB-GEF_CEA_WP3_03.2023	Lecture	teaching exchange of CEA and UB-GEF in POLIS	30
POLIS_POLITO_WP3_05.2023	Lecture	teaching exchange of POLITO 1	24
POLIS_POLITO_WP3_05.2023	Lecture	teaching exchange of POLITO 2	13
RAB_WP_1.2_POLITO_01.04.2023	Meeting	Research Advisory Board meeting in Tirana	19
Teaching Activity_WP_3.3_POLITO_15.05.2023 - 19.05.2023	Teaching Activity	Problem Structuring Methods for facing urban uncertainty	13
Teaching Activity_WP_3.3_POLITO_22.05.23 - 26.05.2023	Teaching Activity	Resilience and Climate Change	15

RSA_WP_3.2_16.06.2023	Conference	GreenFORCE 2023 RSA Annual Conference	11
UBGEF_WP_5.4_20.06.2023	International scientific conference	International Scientific Conference GREEN AGENDA FOR WESTERN BALKANS	189

Figure 2. Dissemination event participants' distribution

3. Communication tools

Initial information for announcing the project initiation was disseminated through the Partners' dissemination channels and their communication tools. These are still being used for wider dissemination, easier communication and higher engagement.

The main communication tools of the project, which were developed and are currently being used, are: 1) The project website; 2) Its Social media accounts; 3) The bi-annual e-newsletter.

3.1. Project website

The project website is the **main media hub** of the project and primary source for feeding its social media as well. The website informs on:

- the project partners and the activities (in all WPs);
- provides resources and methodologies;
- enables policy and societal communication;

It contains information on the products of the project, including the deliverables. Of which, all deliverables open for the public are easily accessible. The site also provides link to the twinning partners websites for local access and more resources on green transition, and to science repositories.

The official GreenFORCE website <https://greenforcetwinning.net/> is fully functional and accessible as of October 31, 2022.

Figure 3. Project Website

Figure 4. Posts Overview

Detailed list per post see in Annex Table 13

3.2. Social media

In addition to the project website, GreenFORCE uses different social media² for distributing information related to our project and for engaging both target groups and the wider public. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube accounts are the media channels used to inform and communicate/disseminate project related information/news.

² Regarding the social media, we apply the Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects (https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf), provided by the European Commission, which includes suggestions and directions how to use social media in Horizon 2020 projects.

Table 3. Social media accounts of GreenFORCE

Twitter	Facebook	Instagram	LinkedIn	YouTube
GreenFORCE Twitter account: @greenforcetp	GreenFORCE Facebook page: Greenforce Twinning Project	GreenFORCE Instagram account: Greenforce_twinning_project	GreenFORCE LinkedIn page: https://www.linkedin.com/in/greenforce-twinning-project/	GreenFORCE YouTube channel: Greenforce Twinning Project (@greenforcetwinnin gproject7598)

Project social media statistics related to each of the tools, such as the number of people reached and engaged are used for monitoring and evaluation purposes as presented below.

Table 4. Social Media GreenForce – cut of date 30/06/2023

Activity no ¹	Type of product ²	Media coverage ³	Number of reached people by social media ⁴	Number of engaged people by social media ⁵
WP3.2 call for paper abstracts to be included in the "Handbook on the Just Green Transition"	Open call/Informative post	n/a	21,522	208
WP4.2 Information regarding the selection of Two local partners have to support the work of CO-PLAN on 'Assessing just green transition impacts and costs'.	informative post	n/a	228	22
WP 3.1 call for abstracts for a Special Issue of the European Journal of Spatial Development	Open call/Informative post	n/a	381	28
WP 5.2 Informative post regarding newsletter publishing	informative post	n/a	1,732	61
WP 1.2 Informative post regarding meeting with the RAB (Research advisory board)	informative post	n/a	1,259	67
WP 3.1 meeting with the Editorial Board of the "Annual Review for Territorial Governance in the Western Balkans"	informative post	n/a	671	29
WP 3.1 Scientific Publication Plan of GreenFORCE	informative post	n/a	521	31
WP5.4 International Scientific Conference GREEN AGENDA informative post	informative post	n/a	406	30
WP 3.3 Problem Structuring Methods for Facing Urban Uncertainty	informative post	n/a	1,506	62
WP 5.4 Information regarding the deadline of abstract submissions for the International Scientific Conference GREEN AGENDA FOR WESTERN BALKANS	Open call/Informative post	n/a	831	57
WP 3.1 Partners from Nordregio and Center for Economic Analyses - CEA come to Co-PLAN Institute for Habitat Development!	Event/Informative post	n/a	1,479	67
WP 3.3 Partners from Center for Economic Analyses - CEA and University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography (Географски факултет) come to Universiteti Polis!	Event/Informative post	n/a	2,230	86
WP 3.3 Resilience and Climate Change	Informative post	n/a	1,538	73
WP 3.3 Partners from Politecnico di Torino come to Universiteti Polis!	Event/Informative post	n/a	1,898	71

WP 3.3 Concluding of teaching exchange	Event/Informative post	n/a	366	24
WP 3.5 Information regarding first summer school	Open call/Informative post	n/a	2,175	95
WP 5.4 Annual Workshop of the Western Balkan Network on Territorial Governance	Event/Informative post	n/a	668	29
WP 1.1 Project Management Board meeting	informative post	n/a	234	20
WP 1.2 Informative post regarding meeting with the RAB Research advisory board)	informative post	n/a	1,813	98
WP 5 Website notification	Informative Post	n/a	818	103
WP 4.1 First co-design workshop (WP4)	Event/Informative post	n/a	1,282	103
WP 4.1 First co-design workshop (WP4) - 2nd post	Event/Informative post	n/a	926	77
WP 3.2 Request for proposals	Open call/informative post	n/a	1,640	86
WP 3.1 SRA workshop	Event/Informative post	n/a	1,421	97
WP 4.1 2nd co-design workshop (WP4)	Event/Informative post	n/a	567	72
WP 4.1 Separate post for both co-design workshops	Event/Informative post	n/a	277	14
WP 5 Post regarding EU-Western Balkans Summit in Tirana	Informative post	n/a	863	59
WP 5 Post regarding National Programme PN Just Transition Fund 2021-2027 in Italy	Informative post	n/a	702	46
WP 5.4 Call for papers for TG Review	Open call/Informative Post	n/a	213	19
WP 5 Spatial Foresight article	Informative Post	n/a	735	52
WP 3.2 Reposting of TG-review- Call for papers	Call for papers	n/a	423	26
WP 3.3 POLITO comes to POLIS (Resilience and Climate Change).	Informative Post	n/a	2,076	105
WP 5.4 RSA conference	Informative Post	n/a	1,111	67
WP 5.4 RSA conference- 2nd post	Informative Post	n/a	2,182	75
TOTAL			56,694	2,159

In addition to the project's social media accounts, the beneficiary organisations from time to time share and repost news disseminated via GreenFORCES' social medias in order to reach a wider audience. This manner is deemed as an effective manner to distribute information to a wider public, even though on a selected scope there is a relatively

wider reach of the general public that cumulatively amount to over 26 thousand social media users. (detailed statistics per partner in annex Table 7.4)

Table 5. Social Media Reach on partners’ social media channels– cut of date 30/06/2023

Activity no ¹	Type of product ²	Media coverage ³	Number of reached people by social media ⁴	Number of engaged people by social media ⁵	link to the media
Social media posts for the GreenFORCE project for informative, dissemination purposes	All social media on own partner channels only (not including GreenFORCE channels)	n/a	40,153	1224	see details in annex
TOTAL - CUMULATIVE			40,153	1224	

In the past year, given the distribution of the reached audience via different social media and the various channels, it can be concluded that the most effective communication by the reached audience is the Facebook channel and Instagram channel of GreenFORCE, accounting for most of the reached audience.

Figure 10. GreenFORCE Social media reach distribution

Figure 11. Social media snapshots

Snapshot of Twitter

Snapshot of Facebook

Snapshot of Instagram

Snapshot of LinkedIn

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3.3. E-newsletters

A biannual newsletter is issued to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly updated on the project’s developments. It will be circulated via the project’s mailing list but also via all partners’ media platforms as links. Each project partner contributes to the content of the newsletter, as it feeds its content mainly from website articles.

The first e-newsletter has been shared by the project account to reach those recipients that have had an interaction with the project such as stakeholders identified, participants in the co-design workshops, etc. which have provided their consent. Furthermore, the partners shared the newsletter with other interested stakeholders within their own network that are interested on the subject and asked for their subscription for future notification.

Figure 12. GreenFORCE Newsletter 1

<https://us11.campaign-archive.com/?u=66731e2150b6a6878776e02fd&id=df4ab88447>

Figure 13. GreenFORCE Newsletter 2

<https://mailchi.mp/838687a9a402/greenforce-newsletter-no-6245862>

Table 6. Newsletter reach

Newsletter	Target	Invitation sent to	Viewed	Subscriptions
Newsletter 1, March 2023	Overall reach for project duration 1000	~600	266	71
Newsletter 2, July 2023		255	218	255

3.4. Press releases/Apearances in the media

Press releases to local newspapers, regional or national TVs, radio stations, as well as web portals, help to expand project information and results of the activities at national and regional level. During the reporting period press release has been shared for 1st conference in Belgrade, Serbia in June 2023.

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<https://shorturl.at/bsCHV>

3.5. Other materials

Printed materials – leaflets, roll-up banner

Project templates – PPT template, word template, newsletter template as a part of the branding guide prepared - available on Trello in the following link <https://trello.com/c/zoPBTKlu>

Figure 14. Example of project’s branding tools used

3.6. Internal communication

3.6.1. Trello platform

Trello platform is used for effective overall project management, coordination of the work between project participants, document management and communication between partners.

Communication within the consortium takes place mostly online, through e-meetings, e-mails and the Trello platform. The use of Trello is necessary for guaranteeing the timely archiving of any kind of outputs related to the implementation of the project at any level, from sub-tasks to deliverables.

Figure 15. GreenFORCE board on Trello platform - snapshot

3.6.2. PMB monthly meetings

In order to update each other on the activities conducted, in progress and planned, regular monthly PMB meetings have taken place... Each monthly meeting is open for every project partner and researcher and it includes presentations of progress per each WP and tasks included in them as well as other issues related to organization, monitoring and managerial questions.

Each monthly meeting organization commences with the preparation of the agenda, where every partner contributes with possible issues to be further addressed, and each meeting is followed by the minutes of the meeting. Each of these are transparently available on our joint Trello platform account. For example the link to one of the PMB documents is <https://trello.com/c/AtgQboJY>.

Besides online, when there is possibility and as planned, the PMB meetings are also organized face-to-face and in synergy with other activities conducted on-the spot.

Figure 16. GreenFORCE PMB meetings and Trello source

Table 7. PMB meetings

PMB meetings	Date	Attendance
PMB 1 – Kick-off	04/7/2022	29 participants
PMB 2	2/9/2022	20 participants
PMB 3	23/9/2022	20 participants
PMB 4	18/10/2022	20 participants
PMB 5	30/11/2023	Hybrid – Tirana physical presence 10 + 14 on line =24 participants
PMB 6	21/11/2022	15 participants
PMB 7	23/01/2023	Hybrid – Skopje physical presence =18 participants
PMB 8	20/2/2023	16 participants
PMB 9	30/3/2023	16 participants
PMB 10	3/5/2023	8 participants
PMB 11	29/05/2023	10 participants
PMB 12	27/06/2023	10 participants
PMB 13	14/07/2023	9 participants

Additional coordination meetings are held for specific activities//tasks between all and some partners and researchers – this is conducted on a needs basis in a bilateral and multilateral level.

4. Dissemination and exploitation activities

Different activities are foreseen to disseminate project results. The activities conducted thus far have been documented in an appropriate table, supported with additional documents as evidence.

The organizers of each event provide a full information package to the participants including draft agenda, letter of invitation and a note on the logistics. Each event is documented: news/event review, agenda, list of participants/trainees, report, gallery, presentations (upon the approval of the presenter), video materials (upon approval of participants).

Table 8. Documentation of dissemination events

Event	Link
Shared strategic research agenda – workshop	https://trello.com/c/yGJpRUL8/47-deliverable-21-shared-strategic-research-agenda
Scientific publication plan co-design workshop	https://trello.com/c/2BAp6bG2/52-deliverable-31-scientific-research-publication-plan
Scientific publication plan co-design workshop (ii)	https://trello.com/c/2BAp6bG2/52-deliverable-31-scientific-research-publication-plan
Seminar & workshop: writing policy briefs	https://trello.com/c/rD5Cbs27/26-task-24-nordregio

4.1. International Scientific Conference

The International Scientific Conference - GREEN AGENDA FOR WESTERN BALKANS, took place from 20 to 22 June 2023 in Belgrade, organized by our partner UB-GEF. The conference presented an important platform and dissemination event on a larger scale for the project. The Conference brought together more than 200 researchers and scholars from Europe and beyond, but other relevant stakeholders including technology leaders, companies, institutions, policy makers concerned with the issues of Green Transition to discuss important topics leading to a successful implementation of the Green Agenda in the Western Balkan countries.

The GREEN AGENDA FOR WESTERN BALKANS International Conference was a comprehensive three-day event including keynotes, panel discussions and high-level networking, and a unique opportunity to promote and disseminate the knowledge of the project as well.

Over the course of the duration of the conference sixty abstracts of scientific papers were presented in the seven sections, including presentations from researchers, PhD and Master students from all partner organizations. The A special session was dedicated to GreenFORCE specifically and co-moderated by Nordregio and POLITICO. The session raised significant attention and concentrated a substantial number of presentations with 11 speakers.

Presentations given in this session covered the following aspects/pillars of the Green Agenda: demography and sustainability relation, comparative review of practices in Europe, spatial planning systems and urbanisation processes, cross-border and transnational cooperation, innovative participative planning, sustainable urban planning, green urban development, urban and agricultural design projects, remote sensing of urbanization, green public spaces, urban gardening, green certification, just green transition in social media, adaptation to climate change, transformation of the tourist system, green tourism, education for green transition and education for climate action.

Figure 17. Excerpt from presentations from GreenFORCE partners in the International Scientific Conference on Green Agenda for Western Balkans, Belgrade

4.2. Local meetings for mapping and engagement

These meetings are directly linked to WP4 to support the participatory mapping, engaging local stakeholders and communities to reveal local knowledge in each WB territory to provide two-way communication, through which information about the project is disseminated, and information for implementation of activities are collected.

The initial round of two Co-Design Workshops (held online, November 2022) on the Conceptualization of the Green Transition in the Western Balkan were attended by total of cumulatively 73 participants including the project partners but other stakeholders as well, with different backgrounds including: policy makers, CSOs, international organizations, scientists and researchers within and outside the consortium.

<https://greenforcetwinning.net/event/co-design-workshop-part-1/>

<https://greenforcetwinning.net/event/co-design-workshop-part2/>

<https://greenforcetwinning.net/2023/05/15/first-meeting-of-the-research-advisory-board-rab/>

Figure 18. Excerpt from the works of the stakeholders on co-design workshop

Table 9. Local meetings for mapping and engagement in the WB countries

CEA – North Macedonia	Meeting with Ministry of Environment (several times), Meeting with Regional Development Bureau, Local Self Government Municipality of Kichevo, Ministry for
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	Economy, Ministry for Labour and Social Policy, Delegation of EU in North Macedonia, Other stakeholders and interested parties, OECD, researchers in the region, NGOs, EBRD, Academia, etc.)
UB-GEF – Serbia	Meetings with City of Kragujevac, Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia, UNDP Serbia, UNDP B&H, Delegation of the European Union to Serbia, Ministry of European Integration of RS, Ministry of Environmental Protection, of Science of RS, Ministry of Technological Development and Innovation of RS, Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure of RS, Embassy of Sweden in Serbia, Regional Cooperation Council, AEBR centre for Balkans, NGOs, Numerous Companies etc.
COPLAN - Albania	Meeting with Director of Tourism at Ministry of Tourism and Environment; Director and representative from National Territorial Planning Agency; Albanian Network of Researchers; PolicyANSWERS Horizon Europe project; Municipality of Tirana; Agency for Energy Efficiency; etc.

GreenFORCE has a research advisory board (RAB), composed of 6 prominent researchers and the first 1st RAB meeting took place in Tirana between March 31st – April 1st, 2023. The RAB meetings although envisaged as having an advisory function, never the less have the role to also disseminate and communicate the project's activity to a wider audience.

4.3. Open-access scientific publications in high-rated journals

The publications prepared in the course of the previous period are freely and openly available via online repositories: 1) ZENODO, 2) GERY.

Figure 19. Zenodo repository GreenFORCE

The screenshot shows the Zenodo search interface. The search bar contains 'greenforce'. The results section shows two items:

- D5.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Strategy** by Aleksandar Djordjevic. It is a project deliverable, open access, and was uploaded on April 1, 2023.
- D1.5 - Data Management Plan** by Merita Toska. It is a project deliverable, open access, and was uploaded on March 29, 2023.

Table 10. List of deliverables and products uploaded in Zenodo

Uploaded	Links
D5.1 Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Strategy	https://zenodo.org/record/7790852
D1.5 - Data Management Plan	https://zenodo.org/record/7781979

D4.1 – Report on Western Balkans Just Green Transition Conceptualisation	https://zenodo.org/record/7790862
D4.2 – Report on Regional Mapping for Green Transition	https://zenodo.org/record/8182750
Dataset for Green Transition Policies, Stakeholders and Practices	https://zenodo.org/record/7785693 https://zenodo.org/record/7782048 https://zenodo.org/record/7785620 https://zenodo.org/record/7786686 https://zenodo.org/record/7785648

Figure 20. GERY repository (GEography RepositoRY University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography) GreenFORCE

GERY - Faculty of Geography Repository
University of Belgrade - Faculty of Geography

GERY / GreenFORCE - Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

GreenFORCE - Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

BROWSE BY

Authors Titles Subjects

Search within this institution/community:

Go

Collections in this community

[GreenFORCE](#)

Recent Submissions

[D4.1 - Report on Western Balkans Just Green Transition Conceptualisation](#)
Toto, Rudina; Imami, Fiona; Poro, Enkela; Garvanlieva, Vesna; Jević, Marija; Gjoka, Rodion; Bejko, Anila (2023)

[Dataset for Green Transition Policies, Stakeholders and Practices in Serbia](#)

Table 11. List of deliverables and products uploaded in GERY

Uploaded	Links
D5.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Strategy	https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/13871390
D1.5 - Data Management Plan	https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/1388
D4.1 – Report on Western Balkans Just Green Transition Conceptualisation	https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/
Dataset for Green Transition Policies, Stakeholders and Practices	https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/1391 https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/1394 https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/1392 https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/1389 https://gery.gef.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/1393

Open-access publications are especially emphasized in the overall project idea. Academics, policy makers and all stakeholders could access them without any financial, legal or technical barriers, and in that way use project research and results.

The GreenFORCE website <https://greenforcetwinning.net/> in the section [Results and Deliverables](#) as well in [Publications](#) include and will include articles summarizing the scientific publications and will be submitted to CORDIS Wire.

4.4. Policy briefs

Policy briefs and recommendations are part of WP2, led by the partner Nordregio, is aimed at targeting mainly policy-makers and practitioners. The Policy briefs are intended as short documents presenting the research results in more approachable language and picking a few policy-relevant messages to be disseminated in cooperation with other project partners, to selected groups of recipients in each WB territory.

The first two joint Policy Brief (PB) are in preparation. The first one is focused on transition fatigue and is based on the findings of the deliverable 4.1 Conceptualization report and the mapping of green transition in the WB countries. The second one focuses on alternative fuels, based on case studies in WP4 and previous research experience in the partnership. The two PBs are planned to be published prior to mid-term reporting and followed with a media campaign to spread the word. The second package of PBs (x3) is planned to be delivered by the end of the project based on the results of WP4.

A list of relevant stakeholders, for the policy briefs to be disseminated to, will be prepared accordingly upon finalization of the documents.

4.5. Participation in external events, scientific congresses and conferences

The events, international conferences, congresses, workshops, exhibitions and fairs are one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy because they allow to connect with stakeholders and the general public, encourage networking and show advances and results of the project. Events also feed of content the communication channels and tools (website, Social Media, press releases) generating great impacts on different audiences.

Each partner is encouraged to attend as many external events related to Green Transition and/or its dimensions as far as possible and at least once during the project duration. It is important to keep the presence of the project in Science, Research and Innovation events that are organized in the WBCs, even after the completion of the project.

All partners: TGWEB 2023 – network annual meeting covered the subject of green transition on territorial development and the project activities

All partners: RSA 2023 Conference participation on a special session for the Western Balkan organized by the project team

All partners: Conference GREEN AGENDA FOR WESTERN BALKANS Belgrade - Special session was dedicated to GreenFORCE co-moderated by Nordregio and PoliTO.

- Nordregio (Alberto Giacometti) contributed with a presentation to 'Section 2: Towards Circular Economy' titled: Change agency in green innovations: Empirical case study on modern wood construction in Sweden and Finland, based on a research project carried by Alberto Giacometti and Hilma Salonen. The presentation argued against a binary structure-agency debate of weather is the formal and informal rules of the game as preconditions leading to new innovations or are the entrepreneurs and businesses leading innovation by challenging the established technological regime by introducing new disruptive technologies/business ideas. Based on empirical evidence, the presentation focused on showing the complementary role that institutions, entrepreneurs and place-based leaders play in driving innovation.

- UB-GEF GreenFORCE researchers Velimir Šećerov, Marija Jeftić, Aleksandar Djordjević, Zora Živanović, Branko Protić, contributed in Session 1: Clean energy sources and climate protection, with the research paper abstract titled Green Transitioning in the City of Kragujevac – Towards sustainable mobility strategy.
- Center for Economic Analyses' researchers Ana Marija Petrovska, Marjan Nikolov, Vesna Garvanlieva Andonova contributed with a presentation in the Session 3: Depollution of air, water and soil, on the subject of hydrological monitoring and water quality management, with the abstract titled Hydrological monitoring and water quality monitoring of lakes and reservoirs in North Macedonia the way towards more efficient monitoring
- Kejt Dhrami, Rea Muka from Co-Plan in the Session 5: Protection of biodiversity and ecosystems presented the Citizen Science practices for participatory ecosystem service evaluation in wetland areas, case of Kune-Vain Lagoon.
- In the Section 6: GreenFORCE - Green agenda and spatial planning, four research paper abstracts were presented, where at least one of the researchers of the partners in the project were authors:
 - *SPATIAL PLANNING SYSTEMS AND URBANISATION PROCESSES IN THE WESTERN BALKANS. WHAT NEXUS?*, Erblin Berisha, Giancarlo Cotella
 - *THE ROLE OF ACTORS IN CROSS-BORDER AND TRANSNATIONAL COOPERATION IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL FIELD IN THE WESTERN BALKANS*, Ilijana Radaković, Erblin Berisha
 - *FOSTERING SUSTAINABLE TRANSITION PATHWAYS VIA URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN PROJECTS: THE CASE OF KISELA VODA, SKOPJE*, Isabella M. Lami, Alessandro Armando, Elena Todella
 - *JUST GREEN TRANSITIONS IN SOCIAL MEDIA BETWEEN THE TERMINOLOGICAL USE IN THE OFFICIAL LANGUAGE AND THE PUBLIC DEBATE*, Yahya Shaker, Simone Persico

Co-PLAN, CEA and Nordregio: As part of the Green-AL project, led by Co-PLAN, partners by Nordregio (Alberto Giacometti) and CEA (Marjan Nikolov) took part in National Forum on Climate Change in Albania. Alberto Giacometti presented the concept of 'just green transition' to the participants.

CEA: Online participation of event Green transition conference by environmental NGO network in Macedonia; Participated on a World bank event in Skopje on the regional WB economic outlook which included the aspects of carbon emission mechanism.

Co-PLAN organized a roundtable on Just Green Transition in the framework of the 'AESOP Congress 2022 Space for Species: Redefining Spatial Justice', organized in Tartu, Estonia, on 25-29 July 2022. The roundtable, titled 'Fit for Green – Social and Territorial Impact of Just Green Transition' brought together esteemed academics and experts, such as Maros Finka, Giancarlo Cotella, Bianca Mitrica, Carlos Tapia and Rodon Miraj to discuss on regional specificities of green transition, and the impact to vulnerable communities.

4.6. Dissemination and exploitation through partners' networking resources

In addition to the dissemination tools of each partner's organisation, GreenFORCE has also well-established dissemination networks through each partner. Partners take into consideration all tools and established relations in the process of dissemination and exploitation and each partner is encouraged to promote, disseminate and exploit the project accordingly with their own networks.

Among the other activities, the partners work towards joint proposals for regional partnership of exploiting the project results into new project proposals, and creation of macroregional partnerships.

5. Monitoring and Evaluation

The progress reports which are part of WP1, as well as the impact measurement and evaluation activities which are also part of WP1, foresee monitoring of all Key Performance Indicators, including the key indicators on communication, dissemination, public engagement and awareness-raising. These activities specifically monitor the progress made against the indicators set in the DCE strategy.

Table 12. KPI achievements of dissemination and communication

KPI of Dissemination and Communication	Target	Achievement to date (Y1)
Prepared branded templates for project memorandum, power point presentation, reports and media posts	Branded templates for the variety of products	Prepared and used Status: completed and ongoing
Project roll-up banner per country (5 in total)	Roll-up banner designed and printed	4/5 prepared and used Status: partial and ongoing
400 project leaflets per country/in total		70 leaflets printed on project factsheet
1.500 website views per year	1500 website	3.192 views achieved (up to 30/06/2023) Status: fully achieved
400 followers on social networks	400 followers	FB 128 followers Instagram 154 followers Linked in: 160 followers (total 452)
at least one post per week on each social network (52 posts per year on each social network)	52 per year	34 in Year 1 per social media prepared and posted + 50 posts on website Status: partial achievement but compensated with web page posts
Distributed e-newsletter 2 times per year (6 in total) through over 1000 – reached	1000 reached	Year 1: Newsletter 1; sent to ~600, subscribers 71, opened 49 Newsletter 2; sent to 255; subscribers 255, opened 109 Status: partially achieved and ongoing
At least 3 local meetings per WB territory (6 in total)	6 meetings	Meeting with the Deputy Minister of the Ministry of Environment and Tourism Mrs. Vilma Bello and the Director of Development Programmes on Environment in the Ministry of Tourism and Environment Klodiana Marika, during the first RAB.
200 stakeholders participating in 4 workshops for co-design	4 co-design workshops	2 completed Achieved: 77 (44+33) Status: completed and ongoing
Drafting and submitting for publication 6 joint scientific papers	6 scientific paper	Status: Pending in preparation
3 open dissemination events including live streaming up to 250 participants, (750 in total)		189 participants in Belgrade Conference Green Agenda for WB
one open-access book application		Status: Application prepared and sent to publisher – completed

2-3 external participation GreenFORCE will be communicated		
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6. Conclusion and recommendations

- The most numbered audience of the first year's activities for dissemination and communication events including meetings, workshops, lectures, conferences, teaching activities etc., are generating audience from different target groups. The participants dominating by number (participants) are for the larger part researchers, both within the consortium however beyond and outside the consortium as well. In the coming period as the project activities will deliver other outputs which are also targeting other target groups it is expected that these will be further included and the distribution of the societal actors' included in the dissemination and communication activities.
- The society at large presented via the general public in the WB region is also a relevant and important target group which is reached more robustly via the communication tools: meetings and web posts plus social media posts. All these communication tools record respectable coverage even beyond the initial plans, thus it is an effective method that should be continued with the equal intensity. The general public reach from partners' social media beyond the project specific social media channels is also an effective outreach for even wider public and should be thus continued. Consider sponsored posts in occasions when a wider public reach will be necessary
- Most effective communication tool/social media channel of the GreenFORCE project are by far Facebook and Instagram, as most effective in reaching wide audience thus the project should continue to focus on these in the future as preferred. The LinkedIn profile reach indicates reasonable reach as well and should be as well kept as it reaches diverse target group to a more professional audience rather than wide public.
- Co-design workshops are one manner of ensuring stakeholder participation and knowledge sharing.
- International conference is effective for direct mass reach for different audiences, nevertheless predominantly for the scientific audience.
- Local meetings for promotion of project are effective in promotion of project and dissemination in each country as a manner not only for data and information collection in implementation of the activities but also for networking and possibilities for potential new partnerships.
- Suggested modifications for the DCE Strategy to be reviewed mid-project implementation, among which:
 - o Review the set measurable targets to comply with the project proposal for e-newsletter subscription to aimed audience of 1000;
 - o and instead of drafting the content for open edited book alter to prepared proposal for edited open access book, consider reporting by gender structure as well for the set measurable targets.

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7. Annexes

Table 13. Web Page Top 50 Posts Overview – for period

Web site: https://greenforcetwinning.net Source: <u>Monster report</u> Period: March 1st 2023 - June 30th 2023		
	Overview Report	1/3/2023-30/06/2023
1	GreenFORCE — FOSTER RESEARCH EXCELLENCE	1,009
2	Call for paper abstracts — GreenFORCE	182
3	News Grid — GreenFORCE	156
4	Publications — GreenFORCE	134
5	International Scientific Conference GREEN AGENDA FOR WESTERN BALKANS being held by UB-GEF — GreenFORCE	128
6	Results and Deliverables — GreenFORCE	103
7	Summer School — GreenFORCE	102
8	Research Topics — GreenFORCE	87
9	International Summer School with the theme 'Cities in Just Green Transitions' and a focus on 'Turin post-carbon transformations' in Turin, Italy on 18-	81
10	Research Advisory Board — GreenFORCE	71
11	Research in Serbia — GreenFORCE	68
12	Event Grid — GreenFORCE	63
13	Consortium & Partners — GreenFORCE	60
14	Research in Albania — GreenFORCE	47
15	Contact Us — GreenFORCE	46
16	Research Advisory Board (RAB) meeting — GreenFORCE	39
17	Twinning Experience — GreenFORCE	38
18	Conceptualizing JUST Green Transition in the Western Balkan — GreenFORCE	37
19	PhD & Master Thesis — GreenFORCE	37
20	Workshop on the co-development of the Shared Strategic Research Agenda — December 2, 2022 — GreenFORCE	33
21	Stakeholders & Actors — GreenFORCE	32
22	Newsletter — GreenFORCE	31
23	Teaching Exchange — GreenFORCE	30
24	Co-Design Workshops on the Conceptualization of the Green Transition in the Western Balkan — GreenFORCE	29
25	Editorial — Our endeavor to a Just Green Transition — GreenFORCE	24
26	From Research to Policy — Workshop on Policy writing — GreenFORCE	24
27	TG-REVIEW Call for Papers 2023 — GreenFORCE	23
28	Research in North Macedonia — GreenFORCE	23
29	Summer School in Torino — September 2023 — GreenFORCE	22
30	Workshop on Scientific Research Publication Plan — December 1, 2022 — GreenFORCE	21
31	Research in Montenegro — GreenFORCE	20
32	Relevant Data & Legislations — GreenFORCE	19
33	GreenFORCE Project kick started on July 2022 — GreenFORCE	18
34	Joint teaching events and exchanges — from March to November 2023 — GreenFORCE	15
35	Research in Bosnia and Herzegovina — GreenFORCE	15
36	Call for paper abstracts — GreenFORCE	12
37	Workshop on the Shared Research Agenda — January 23, 2023 — GreenFORCE	11
38	New local partners in the Western Balkans — GreenFORCE	10
39	Green Force — GreenFORCE	10

40	RSA Annual Conference / Special Session — June 2023 — GreenFORCE	10
41	Will be updated soon — GreenFORCE	9
42	Workshop on Scientific Research Publication Plan — January 23, 2023 — GreenFORCE	9
43	GreenFORCE — FOSTER RESEARCH EXCELLENCE	9
44	Key Crosscutting Issues — GreenFORCE	9
45	Research Advisory Board (RAB) meeting — GreenFORCE	8
46	Search Results for “International Summer School” — GreenFORCE	7
47	From Research to Policy — Workshop on Policy writing — GreenFORCE	6
48	Editorial — GreenFORCE	6
49	Research Advisory Board -GreenFORCE	6
50	Call for paper abstracts — GreenFORCE	5
	TOTAL	2,994

Table 14. Table for detailed reporting on dissemination events and activities - year 1

Dissemination and communication activities linked to the project										Estimated number of participant/Estimated number of reach														Actual number of participants
ID (PXX_XX_of.nn.yyyy)	Type of activity	Title	Channel/ Location	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Organizer	Impact (National/ International)	Additional comments (if you chose other, please specify the type of activity)	Evidence/Link	Type of post (Original/ Repost/ Retweet/ and choose BEDES* and the source*)	Researchers from the consortium	Researchers beyond Consortium	Students	Scientists	Policy makers	Societal actors related to green transition	Industries	Media	Civil society organizations	Other	Participants age groups	Gender ratio MF	Countries covered by the activity		
Co-PLAN_WP1_1.1_04.07.2022	Meeting	Kick-off meeting of GreenFORCE Project	Zoom/Online	04.07.2022	Lead/Co-PLAN	international		Minutes on: https://trello.com/c/WeXqAba	original	22	3	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	4	various	14/15	WB/EU	29	
CO-PLAN_WP4_1_08.11.2022	workshop	Co-Design Workshop on the Conceptualization of the Green Transition in the Western Balkan – part 1	online + mural	08.11.2022	Lead/Co-Plan	international		Report available on: https://trello.com/c/UjswtLov	original	20	10	2	1	8	2	0	0	8	0	various	4/8/52	WB/EU	44	
CO-PLAN_WP4_1_22.11.2022	workshop	Co-Design Workshop on the Conceptualization of the Green Transition in the Western Balkan – part 2	online + mural	22.11.2022	Lead/Co-Plan	international		Report available on: https://trello.com/c/UjswtLov	original	22	3	2	1	5	1	0	0	5	0	various	4/2/58	WB/EU	33	
POLITO_WP_3_1/1_01.12.2022	Collaboration meeting	Scientific Publication Plan Co-Design Workshop	hybrid + Tirana	01.12.2022	Politecnico di Torino, Italy	international		Report available on: https://trello.com/c/5VAlyHy	original	22	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	various	55/45	WB/EU	22	
NORD_COPLAN_WP_2_1/1_02.12.2022	Collaboration meeting	Shared Strategic Research Agenda - Workshop	Tirana Nordregio	02.12.2022	Sweden/ Co-PLAN	international		Report available on: https://trello.com/c/MGnjOXvUj/s-shared-strategic-research-agenda-workshop	original	20	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	various	50/50	WB/EU	20	
POLITO_WP_3_1_23.01.2023	Collaboration meeting	Scientific Publication Plan Co-Design Workshop	hybrid + Skopje	23.01.2023	Politecnico di Torino, Italy	international		Report available on: https://trello.com/c/JJzQxHN	original	19	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	various	58/42	WB/EU	19	
NORD_WP_2_4/1_24.01.2023	Collaboration meeting	SEMINAR & WORKSHOP: Writing policy briefs	hybrid + Skopje	24.01.2023	Nordregio, Sweden	international		Report available on: https://trello.com/c/stz3kZVU	original	18	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	various	55/45	WB/EU	18	
NORD_COPLAN_WP_2_1/2_24.01.2023	Collaboration meeting	Shared Strategic Research Agenda - Workshop	hybrid + Skopje	24.01.2023	Nordregio, Sweden/ Co-PLAN	international		Report available on: https://trello.com/c/MGnjOXvUj/s-shared-strategic-research-agenda-workshop	original	18	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	various	55/45	WB/EU	18	
POLITO_Co-PLAN_WP1_1.2_01.04.2023	Collaborative meeting	Research Advisory Board meeting	Hybrid/ Tirana	01.04.2023	Co-PLAN/POLITO	international		https://www.facebook.com/p/ernalink.php?story_fbid=pfbi	Original	13	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	various	10/9	WB/EU	19	
Nordregio_Co-PLAN_WP2_03.2023	Forum	National Forum 'Climate change in Albania'	in person/Romania	28.03.2023	Nordregio/C o-PLAN	international		https://www.facebook.com/p/ernalink.php?story_fbid=pfbi	Original	7	15	6	1	10	28	4	1	15	8	various	43/52	WB/EU	95	
Nordregio_Co-PLAN_WP2_03.2023	Workshop	Alberto workshop in POLIS	in person/Tirana	29.03.2023	Nordregio/C o-PLAN	international		https://www.facebook.com/p/ernalink.php?story_fbid=pfbi	Original	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	various	05/06	WB/EU	11	
POLIS_UB-GEF_CEA_WP3_03.2023	Lecture	teaching exchange of CEA and UB-GEF in POLIS	in person/POLIS	27/28.03.2023	POLIS	international		https://www.facebook.com/p/ernalink.php?story_fbid=pfbi	Original	4	2	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	various	09/21	WB	30	
POLIS_POLITO_WP3_05.2023	Lecture	teaching exchange of POLITO 1	in person/POLIS	15 - 19.05.2023	POLIS	international		https://www.facebook.com/p/ernalink.php?story_fbid=pfbi	Original	2	0	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	various	05/19	WB/EU	24	
POLIS_POLITO_WP3_05.2023	Lecture	teaching exchange of POLITO 2	Online/POLIS	22-26.05.2023	POLIS	international		https://www.facebook.com/p/ernalink.php?story_fbid=pfbi	Original	2	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	05/08	WB/EU	13	

Table 15. Table for detailed reporting on dissemination events and activities year 1 - continued

Dissemination and communication activities linked to the project											Estimated number of participant/Estimated number of reach											Actual number of participants	
ID (PXX_XX_8dmm/yyyy)	Type of activity	Title	Channel/Location	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Organizer	Impact (National/International)	Additional comments (if you have any please specify the type of activity)	Evidence/Link	Type of post (Original post/Repost) *If you choose REPOST, add the source	Researchers from the Consortium	Researchers beyond Consortium	Students	Scientists	Policy makers	Societal actors related to green transition	Industries	Media	Civil society organizations	Other	Participants age groups	Gender ratio MF	Countries covered by the activity	Actual number of participants
RAB_WP_1.2_POLITO_01.04.2023	Meeting	Research Advisory Board meeting in Tirana	Tirana/online	01.04.2023	Coplan/POLITO	international		Event report (to be drafted according to the project)	original	12	7	0	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	various	40/60	WB/EU	19
Teaching Activity_WP_3.3_POLITO_15.05.2023 - 19.05.2023	Teaching Activity	Problem Structuring Methods for facing urban uncertainty	Tirana	15.05.2023 - 19.05.2023	Torino, Italy; U_POLIS, Tirana	National		Teaching report and ppt (to be drafted according to the project timeline)	original	3	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	various	45/55	WB	13
Teaching Activity_WP_3.3_POLITO_22.05.23 - 26.05.2023	Teaching Activity	Resilience and Climate Change	Tirana	22.05.23 - 26.05.2023	Torino, Italy; U_POLIS, Tirana	National		Teaching report and ppt (to be drafted according to the project timeline)	original	3	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		48/52	WB	15
RSA_WP_3.2_16.06.2023	Conference	GreenFORCE 2023 RSA Annual Conference	In person Ljubljana	16.06.2023	RSA	international		Event report	original	5	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	various	64/36	WB/EU	11
UBGEF_WP_5.4_20.06.2023	International scientific conference	International Scientific Conference GREEN AGENDA FOR WESTERN BALKANS	Belgrade, Serbia	20-22/06/2023	University of Belgrade - Faculty of	International	/	GreenFORCEhttps://greenforcetwinning.net/	original	16	63	7	19	19		26	2	7	30	various	44/56	Serbia, BiH, Italy, Slovakia	189

Table 16. Social Media Reach on partners’ social media channels – cut of date 30/06/2023

Partner: CO-PLAN

Activity no ¹	Type of product ²	Media coverage ³	Number of reached people by social media ⁴	Number of engaged people by social media ⁵	Link to the media
Kick off meeting	Event/informative post	n/a	4797	129	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid02TBxRfLDZ7qzfxTxD0BZ8tGqFbTbcnJQab2MqX84EgnbBXYDHP2XivPMS2OxZLqWHI https://www.instagram.com/p/CfomCoCtwSv/
PMB #3	Event/informative post	n/a	972	31	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid02kyRoFN1kmyPWaEsis2HZbdwbaogC7Dk4J96qQ47YppMNsCDJbkt52DuxoNVMbyRI https://www.instagram.com/p/Ci3LBJ4rxt2/
Update on website functionality	Informative post	n/a	1214	45	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid02Q8GjsaXJFgrempe4RB6xxYfg48o9p5bbwm1pWTa9Mg5zYKmbBBAQhQeM3Qu2bwwml
Co-design workshop (WP4)	Event/informative post	n/a	791	17	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid096SxNv7YvEFAePdyxUJzNmvtqsmF7HPsQuXJ223mLyx3p57uvHXbTpgZwVWGDqgI https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6995754283539283968/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1558990715219922944
Request for proposals	Open call	n/a	2292	55	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid02FXHoobsxwbKNA3j5vd51RUdvKEkEP6yHUiyFp6ZCSSJ7z8cZT3xTtLCwgm95fhPVI https://www.instagram.com/p/CIERMBxNoVu/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6999026375256870912/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1593262169516187648
Local partner declaration	Informative post	n/a	401	5	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7033708081666568192/
Co-design workshop (WP4)	Event/informative post	n/a	317	9	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid038J998YJnRooddjUSpvs5TQsWk5WRmCBM3iyF6vN37fqKRkc6Grdcnrz61Cj3cl
Call for paper abstracts (WP3)	Open call	n/a	369	9	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid02brm26R1wLMvxrEVUdZ8UfbATNzdSuyUrWzrskvdTRzvcdirsatPs2Vms7KjfoEA1I https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1622920576166727682
Meeting of GreenFORCE with TG-WeB board	Event/informative post	n/a	1402	51	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbid02dYjChqSU6ZuqTkvj1JqbiNmdeX537EQ5RadBYJHawX7ZWjoxXqVUaRppW3Z6vI https://www.instagram.com/p/CqAYxzMt9Ta/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7043528914425528320/?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_u

					pdateV2%3A%28urn%3Ali%3AActivity%3A7043528914425528320%2CFEED_DETAIL%2CEMPTY%2CDEFAULT%2Cfalse%29
					https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1637764429616914432
RAB Meeting preparations	Event/informative post	n/a	1063	27	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbido21ALwicsnRgE46gQ4SOVWMJ2uYAHHjoXctXkAqgRmZVrwrDqWcPnNqfNqmUpU5! https://www.instagram.com/p/CqAZB9SNo8a/
					https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7043521712348348416/
					https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1637756896059748352
Newsletter notification	Informative post	n/a	1160	41	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbido2kjl3GN27iATTUKBRKYeBeZkdR9JgbMXUwVvA2SAHWUfpoRUsYgrMRmMDiMguZPLI https://www.instagram.com/p/CqSi7h2tM9j/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7046074801337044992/
					https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1640308923130413056
RAB meeting details	Informative post	n/a	993	38	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbidom6evz8QCGvzf8m4BxdF48GwpdBSrWgrcYhFszgKCAhnzW6HzWKJZdLWduZBFdasHl https://www.instagram.com/p/Cqll18NqF5/
Teaching exchange notification (WP3)	Informative post	n/a	685	35	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbidoBwFDbWnMzT8GQoHbj7XitWj6XNduE8thBjuzwM1Lnci4SDqbFbusK4gNq1cEDsYl https://www.instagram.com/p/Cq8Vqs2NkEY/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7052195624808513536/
					https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1646430459641974784
TG Review call for papers	Open call	n/a	3511	100	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbidoMMjWathhPdsGqZxE7EbAmgNaZnFzqH46ZfTSQF1trKd8Q1x2HZdHQbgAHJNje8J6l https://www.instagram.com/p/CrLELxltgmy/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7054027563374903296/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1648264351344721920
Nordregio and CEA secondment in Albania	Event/Informative post	n/a	1063	37	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbido2Njtk6Rn7P6YRVir2D8SXtomUWjaaJND7jTijqBxokEDTSzsxskmyVTNUDJq3TURwl https://www.instagram.com/p/CrIP2SItHLs/
					https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057712252426051585/
					https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1651946238869118977
Teaching exchange (CEA and UB-GEF) (WP3)	Informative post	n/a	1087	37	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbido2G8EkJTPr24RRiBfxqpfQz4xnpUrdSVkw6uUGVNBhmemv33hDycywtEiyXYrC2mWNI

					https://www.instagram.com/p/Croof_atJEI/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059911910766317568/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1654146483858309122
TG-WeB Meeting in Skopje	Event/Informative post	n/a	2523	116	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbido2toYLWzEhtjncm6YjE9x748vbhrCgGYNBuUPBcVcqgHetLF1pdFz8r1iq8haRqXUW/ https://www.instagram.com/p/CsGQJMkN82M/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062355008121372672/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1656598462853423104
TG-WeB Meeting in Skopje (2 nd post)	Event/Informative post	n/a	917	16	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062794772574347264/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1657030277703561216
Teaching exchange notification (WP3)	Informative post	n/a	847	26	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbidoiKTeXkmkALmxyhKrRfbkqjswktpWpYpFiRAYQbo5NEeqhBzU3kvbK6pENYqePMc/ https://www.instagram.com/p/CslvEjbtGj/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062720961430601728/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1656955742300061696
Teaching exchange occurrence (WP3)	Event/Informative post	n/a	1284	32	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbido2YtY1QooMJ83XrQaTbqRUEnaLVPgGhaChtJQAxEuWPInqLeVvZ3BjDAkadWik69fgV/ https://www.instagram.com/p/CsRCooXNUzW/ https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7063873639321866240/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1658108113239654400
TG Review extended call for papers deadline	Open call	n/a	1054	44	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbidoq3T3xia3D98UNHWQa1xWNRUjNw8kKnayS7MSK2yM5tzWRHGpwBvmEWZXV51DyUP7/ https://www.instagram.com/p/CtZDRZDlmos/ https://twitter.com/co_plan/status/1668244090448752640
RSA conference participation	Event/Informative post	n/a	330	4	https://www.facebook.com/CoPLANTirana/posts/pfbidoam6FPuUvXVYSejvJ3gvHrjR6b3Ukg7whDTtmgKj5faiEZrQPFeju4vNhvyCwkj1X/
WB JGT article	Informative post	n/a	314	7	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7069323567317868545/
TOTAL			13,545	570	

Partner: CEA

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Activity no ¹	Type of product ²	Media coverage ³	Number of reached people by social media ⁴	Number of engaged people by social media ⁵	link to the media
WP1_Kick off meeting	Informative post	n/a	355	Reaction: 25	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbido2g6v5TM59AErXVSCXciwswfGocpeUKaN5eNJUouGXjnw2QCBpsshvJgU4AGOmYpC7l
WP5_Information for GreenFORCE website functional	Informative post	n/a	156	Reaction: 1	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbido2WYZkLc38kos14hZ3SiqqFXnULpD8eTz5kjc5PpGhdPUWxRLTjSGRvNsqh4PqdQbjl
WP5_Information for GreenFORCE FB page functional	Informative post	n/a	166	Reaction: 5	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbidoCtq7xnOqp66CypnXqzYtX9tp2T8AU8N1q8qVroCcsSAuan6931RDSWur11anHTbYl
WP4.1_Co-design Workshop 2	Workshop - Co-design workshop 2	n/a	213	Reaction: 2	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbidoiWhMB09sZTUdRpg4EmpB3fx9oeVtqzfnH3hULaGWSLu8HWqWWJfr7jdtY7kbNjI
WP3.1_Scientific Publication Co-design Workshop 1	Workshop - Tirana Hybrid 1/12/2022	n/a	235	Reaction 4:	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbido2K7mYfnuPeMizTCR1EhxcNtjnzGSS5BwzB1FBkmwaTmJL5aqAU265SE5S5jCuuTcZl
WP4Workshop on SRA process and Structure	Workshop - Skopje Hybrid 23-24/1/2023	n/a	1,033	Reaction: 17	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbidoroLdvxcFExBTS1D8VjFmLpDMCyKKKVL5VXDjHqhPyGyni5THXvEi8506HetXAPwI
WP3.1_Scientific Publication Co-design Workshop 2 & WP2.4_Policy brief writing	Workshop - Skopje Hybrid 23-24/1/2024	n/a	977	Reaction: 20	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbido3BH9LbBPU1pwyaes5zBzxxuu3KATUgZvsFL6S4Fd7FP4gkfm963aCoazCDDQdI
WP3.2_Call for papers -scientific call for external scientists	Informative post	n/a	155	Reaction: 1	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbido27S7vMpnG7M555hg7jnl13zYEgXfzixGxtF8MgymndEYTFt3iv4gTzkBLGwC1Z5J5I
WP5_International conference Belgrade Call for Abstracts	Informative post	n/a	196	Reaction: 3	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbidoUqLdSyzeBE5bJQPcTcrjKXNxlx7P5zGmqd1XSAmL7jvjVq1cokoYbYYy3PFfoul
WP5_TGWEB Annual Conference	Informative post	n/a	161	Reaction: 4	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbido36UKTF5sTqRzJzQyLzPvUYj4UngUbktioJowJhzB7Hp5dcim4D3oTCcbct79KNi8HI
WP5_International conference Belgrade	Informative post	n/a	550	39	https://www.facebook.com/ceaorgmk/posts/pfbidoFFtNhxwKMSaWAtc2RYq67NgatrAZvFh7cMZGRHTqziF45faoPcGygbgetAMYCfjl
TOTAL			4,197	121	

Partner: POLITO

Activity no ¹	Type of product ²	Media coverage ³	Number of reached people by social media ⁴	Number of engaged people by social media ⁵	link to the media
WP 5.1 Crosslinks among websites informative post (13/12/2022)	Facebook (R3C Polito)	n/a	243	2	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=609021901022933&set=a.537697518155372

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	Instagram (R3C Polito)	n/a	166	9	https://www.instagram.com/p/CmGwBLFsFki/
	LinkedIn (R3C Polito)	n/a	91	3	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/r3c-responsible-risk-resilience-centre_r3cabrpolito-greenforceproject-westernabrbalkans-activity-7008383092289638401-u8bV?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
WP 3.1 Scientific Publication Plan of GreenFORCE (30/01/2022)	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	17	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/483369134010939
	Instagram (DIST Polito)	n/a	1026	43	https://www.instagram.com/p/CoCZ-PENqjx/
	LinkedIn (DIST Polito)	n/a	904	28	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dipartimento-interateneo-di-scienze-progetto-e-politiche-del-territorio-dist_greenforcetwinning-greenforce-greencommunity-activity-7025789304266178560-Et6Z?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
	LinkedIn (R3C Polito)	n/a	91	6	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/r3c-responsible-risk-resilience-centre_greenforcetwinning-greenforce-greencommunity-activity-7025813842395832320-G5K?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
WP 3.2 call for paper abstracts to be included in the “Handbook on the Just Green Transition” (07/02/2023)	Website (DIST Polito)	n/a	-	-	https://www.dist.polito.it/news/(idnews)/20172
	Facebook (DIST Polito)		555	2	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/498072819207237
	Instagram (DIST Polito)	n/a	1026	3	https://www.instagram.com/p/Co4S4XMo2Em/?hl=it
	Website (R3C Polito)		-	-	http://www.r3c.polito.it/news/call-abstracts-handbook-just-green-transition-greenforce-project
	Facebook (R3C Polito)	n/a	243	4	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=649067723685017&set=a.537697518155372
	Instagram (R3C Polito)		166	1	https://www.instagram.com/p/CoZWfv-sXb4/
WP5.4 International Scientific Conference GREEN AGENDA informative post (02/03/2023)	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	22	https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=504547141893138&set=pb.100070135694202.-2207520000.&type=3
	Instagram (DIST Polito)	n/a	1026	12	https://www.instagram.com/p/CpR7ixuoJgK/?hl=it
	Website (DIST Polito)	n/a	-	-	https://www.dist.polito.it/news/(idnews)/20276
WP 1.2 Informative post regarding meeting with the RAB (Research advisory board) (05/04/2023)	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	2	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/524122043268981
WP 3.3 Problem Structuring Methods for Facing Urban Uncertainty (12/04/2023)	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	6	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/528630136151505
WP 5.1 call for papers informative post (20/04/2023)	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	4	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/532334119114440
WP 3.3 Resilience and Climate Change (12/05/2023)	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	4	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/546920390989146
	Facebook (R3C Polito)	n/a	243	3	https://www.facebook.com/r3cpolito/posts/703734361551686
WP 3.3 Partners from Politecnico di Torino come to Universiteti Polis! (13/06/2023)	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	6	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/567863305561521
	Facebook (DIST Polito)	n/a	555	2	https://www.facebook.com/DIST.polito.unito/posts/573230258358159

WP5.4 International Scientific Conference GREEN AGENDA informative post (29/06/2023)	Instagram (DIST Polito)	n/a	1,026	10	https://www.instagram.com/p/CuEZ8UFNhVA/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igshid=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==
	LinkedIn (DIST Polito)	n/a	904	5	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dipartimento-interateneo-disciENZE-progetto-e-politiche-del-territorio-dist-polito-unito-conference-activity-7080114408806338560-K-HS?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
TOTAL			12,150	194	

Partner: UB-GEF

Activity no ¹	Type of product ²	Media coverage ³	Number of reached people by social media ⁴	Number of engaged people by social media ⁵	link to the media
WP1_Project Management Board Meetings	Informative post	n/a	1,961	Reaction: 104	https://www.instagram.com/p/CjAbgCPM8Co/
WP5_TGWEB Annual Conference	Informative post	n/a	854	Reaction: 105	https://www.instagram.com/p/CsalzpEMh-4/
WP5_International conference Belgrade Announcement of the beginning of the conference.	Informative post	n/a	909	Reaction: 130	https://www.instagram.com/p/CtwGXG9Mvlu/
Instagram story - Scientific Publication Plan Co-Design Workshop	Instagram story	n/a	428	n/a	
Instagram story - Kick off	Instagram story	n/a	417	n/a	
Instagram story – SRA	Instagram story	n/a	513	n/a	
Instagram story - Call for abstracts	Instagram story	n/a	559	n/a	
Instagram story - Call for international conference 1	Instagram story	n/a	507	n/a	
Instagram story - Call for international conference 2	Instagram story	n/a	559	n/a	
Instagram story - Summer school call 1	Instagram story	n/a	669	n/a	
Instagram story - Summer school call 2	Instagram story	n/a	870	n/a	
Instagram story - Summer school call 3	Instagram story	n/a	635	n/a	
Instagram story - International conference	Instagram story	n/a	782	n/a	
Instagram story - International conference special session	Instagram story	n/a	564	n/a	
TOTAL			10,227	339	

